

Forecast Air Pollution in Smart City Using Deep Learning Techniques: A Review

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 04, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords</p> <p>Air pollution Smart city Air quality prediction;</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4737746</p>	<p><i>Air pollution is a type of environmental challenges that considered one of the crucial problems confronting human life in urban areas. This problem has been resulted from the abundance of automobiles, emissions from industrial production, combustion of petroleum products for the transportation and electricity generation. This paper will be considering all studies conducted recently to detect and predict the air pollution in smart cities. With the rapid development of deep learning technologies and their usage in almost all aspects of life, it has become possible to predict air quality in smart cities using deep learning techniques. This paper investigates the studies related to deep learning techniques under the framework of smart cities. This paper concluding that the majority of the researchers have a tendency to use more sophisticated and intelligent methods to handle the problem of the air pollution detection in early stages while few researches incorporated the simple techniques. The main predicted pollutants were $PM_{2.5}$.</i></p>

Introduction

The number of people moving to cities as reported by the Urban Population website for the year 2019 was 55.714% [1]. As the UN revealed, it is expected that 68% of the world's population will live in urban cities by 2050 [2]. This population movement would be causing several health problems, transportation and air quality problems. In order to solve these issues, smart cities principle has been found, and it could be defined in different definitions like "A smart city is a city in which there are six main components including smart environment, smart economy, smart transportation, smart management, smart life, and smart citizens" [3]. Another definition is "smart computing technologies that used to make the services of a city and critical infrastructure components whose include city administration, education, real estate, public safety, interconnected, transportation, healthcare, and utilities more intelligent, and efficient" [4].

Through the data provided by smart cities, we can notice that air pollution is one of the main problems in these cities, which is involved in many fields. According to

The World Health Organization (WHO), there are seven million people dying around the world due to air pollution, as the data showed that 9 out of 10 people breathe polluted air that exceeds the limits of WHO guidelines [5]. Also, the concept of the Air Quality Index (AQI) was developed by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), which is a color-coded indicator to indicate and predict daily air quality, as it takes the relationship between a group of pollutants that are considered to have a major impact on people, and these pollutants are ozone (O₃), particulate matter (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀), carbon monoxide (CO), Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and sulfur dioxide (SO₂).

AQI focuses on the health effects caused by these pollutants, which may occur hours or days after they breathe. The AQI scale that is used to measure the pollution is ranging between 0 and 500. As the AQI levels goes up, the risks of air pollution increase, accordingly [6]. Short-term exposure to pollutants causes health damage such as COPD (Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease), cough, shortness of breath, wheezing, asthma, and respiratory disease. When it comes to the long-term effect of the air pollution exposure, this exposure might cause greater damage to health such as chronic asthma, pulmonary insufficiency, and cardiovascular diseases, etc... [7,47]. Air pollution does not only affect humans and animals, but it has a direct effect on plants. Plants are affected by exposure to long-term pollution, as plant leaves are damaged because it is the part most susceptible to pollution [48].

Therefore, obtaining air quality data is very important to take preventive measures, but the task of obtaining and analyzing this data remains a difficult task. To analyze the data with high efficiency and accuracy, production methods and techniques must be used to reach the desired results.

The goal of this paper is to review articles related to air pollution prediction in smart cities using deep learning techniques. Deep learning as a machine learning methodology is considered a successful tool to predict air pollution as it has the capability to solve problems of big data, which can be defined by 3Vs (Volume, Variety, and Velocity) [50]. Moreover, deep learning techniques are based on the parallel processing principles in which the complex predication problems can be solved via multiple processing units or layers. In this review paper, the model type, the gases detected and the time steps are taken into account.

In the rest of the paper, section two contains basic definition of deep learning, section three contains a review of some research papers, sections four and five are discussion and conclusion.

2 Deep Learning

Deep Learning (DL) It is a field of ML [49][53]. "A new approach to representation of learning from data places the emphasis on learning successive layers of increasingly meaningful representations "[8][51]. Deep learning is highly accurate because it uses many non-linear layers to extract and transform features [9].

To compare between deep learning and machine learning, there are two main differences: first, the size of data, where deep learning uses big data, unlike machine learning, and secondly, problem-solving methods in deep learning, there is a synchronization process between the layers, because as we mentioned earlier, deep learning consists of many hidden layers while machine learning is based perform operations in a single layer [9]. There are four main types of deep learning: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning, and reinforcement learning.

Supervised learning: It is learning from existing data and using it to train a neural network to predict unexpected data outcomes [43]. Classification and regression are the two most common applications of supervised learning [8].

unsupervised learning: It is a type of learning where it develops the system, organizes the data, and searches for common and interesting features in the data [43]. Its most popular applications are clustering and dimensional reduction [8].

semi-supervised learning: It is the process of combining unclassified data in the event that there are few data and a large amount of unnamed data [43,44].

reinforcement learning: In this type of learning, the "agent" is given the ability to learn from the surrounding environment, where the agent learns from the environment by implementing "actions" leading to the achievement of the largest number of "rewards" and it does so through the explored and exploited knowledge that it learns through experiences to maximize the rewards. So, it can be said that this occurs between supervised learning and unsupervised learning [43].

3Deep Learning for Air Pollution Prediction

Many models and techniques have been used to predict air pollution, like (LSTM, STDL, CNN, SAE). We will briefly explain each model and the research papers related to it.

3.1 Long-Sort-Term-Memory (LSTM)

It is one of the most used methods to predict air pollution, a type of RNN, which is used to solve the vanishing gradient problem. LSTM consists of 3 main parts, the input gate, the output gate, and the forget gate, which regulate the flow of information in and out of the cell. These parts are located in memory blocks instead of neurons in the hidden layer with standard RNN. LSTM used Time-series data, pollution information, and observations to predict the future [9] [10]. Figure (1) show LSTM Architecture.

Figure (1) LSTM Architecture [11]

A deep learning model for air quality prediction in smart cities [10]. In 2017 to predict O_3 and NO_2 , KÖK, ŞİMŞEK and ÖZDEMİR used LSTM model to predict future Air Quality in smart city. In the same time used Support Vector Regressor (SVR) which is a “method used for classifying linear and non-linear data “, to compare the result with LSTM. To begin with, they construct the best LSTM model by testing various hyperparameters. The used dataset content 17568 samples whose included eight features (O_3 , particulate matter ($PM_{2.5}$, PM_{10}), CO , SO_2 , NO_2 , longitude, latitude and timestamp) the dataset collected from IOT devises in smart city at five-minute intervals. MAE (Mean Absolute Error) and RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error) they used to evaluate performance. The results for ozone using RMSE and MSE were (3.26, 2.81) respectively, and for NO_2 it was (3.76, 3.11). SVR results were at levels higher than LSTM. So, the accuracy of the LSTM and SVR respectively was 95% and 92.95%. In the end, the LSTM model has more advantages in terms of accuracy and predictability due to its long-term memory even if it consists of simple network architecture.

Deep Learning Model to Estimate Air Pollution Using M-BP to Fill in Missing Proxy Urban Data[12]. In Hong Kong and China 2017 a deep learning system was proposed using available urban data as proxy data. The deep learning model consisted of LSTM and also M-BP algorithm was used to retrieve or fill in the lost data. AQI data were collected from 16 AQM (Air Quality Monitoring) stations in Hong Kong, which are the hourly data, including ($PM_{2.5}$, NO_2 , SO_2 , PM_{10}) that the M-BP algorithm reduced the error rate to 0.8% by adding this model achieved high speed with training up to 5 hours.

A Deep Learning Approach for Forecasting Air Pollution in South Korea Using LSTM[13]. Some researchers from South Korea in 2018 tried to predict $PM_{2.5}$ levels using RNN and LSTM by an Encoder-Decoder (En-De) model. This model allows multiple layers of RNN to be stacked on top of each other to increase accuracy. This model was implemented on two sets of data from multiple sources from 2008 to 2018 that contain 30 million records filtered into 27.936 rows of data to be divided and used to train and test the model. The evaluation metrics used is RAE and RMSE, using two layers of RNN, 24 encoding timesteps for coding and 8 decoding timesteps, the RMSE is 12.41 and 13.47. And by using En-De, 24 hours in the past to 16&20 future timesteps the results of two RNN are 12.85, 12.79 in RMSE.

Forecasting air quality time series using deep learning [14]. To find the ozone concentration of 8 hours in the future in Kuwait, a group of researchers in Canada in 2018 proposed a deep learning model using RNN and LSTM. Measuring the error rate by using MAE and compared the results with previous research using machine learning techniques. The data were collected by using OPSIS Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy (DOAS) analyzers. It is a device placed in Kuwait. The data used in the research were read in hours from 2012 to September 2014. The missing data was processed using a first-class computation technique that relies on previous time series to fill in the gaps. The features used to train LSTM were reduced from 25 to 5. This reduction in the features resulted in a significant reduction in the error rate.

A new method for prediction of air pollution based on intelligent computation[16]. A group of Iraqi researchers proposed a new model, which is Smart Air Quality Prediction Model (SAQPM) consisting of the computation-based Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) that relies on unsupervised learning and LSTM algorithm. This model predicts the next two days and for six pollutant concentrations ($PM_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , SO_2 , NO_2 , CO). The data used is data from KDD which is data from 35 stations in China. As a first step, the data are collected and the missing values are processed, so that the LSTM model and PSO are built. The Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (SMAPE) was used, which made a good evaluation of the prediction over 48 hours. The model is new and used new methods.

An LSTM-based aggregated model for air pollution forecasting[17]. This paper has used Aggregated LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) (ALSTM) model to predict $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations for 1-8h in the future in Taiwan the model. The model of the aggregated ALSTM includes two categories and it's similar to that of voting, this

aggregated model will provide the final predicted value by merging the predictive features. The two categories are: mixing and aggregation-learning. The first category "mixing" trains an independent model to produce predictive features, and then uses these predictive features to train a model to combine it into a predicted final value. Further, the category of aggregation learning is responsible for synchronizing the predictive features from the sub-models provide a final composite dataset. The training data from 2012-2017 and it was included 17 features and the model was tested on data was collected in 2018. The ALSTM was compared with the SVR, GBTR, and LSTM by using different evaluation metrics such as MAE, RMSE, and MAPE the result showed that ALSTM model can improve the accuracy of forecasting.

Air quality predictions with a semi-supervised bidirectional LSTM neural network[20]. the proposed system that used herein called EMD-Bi-LSTM which is semi-supervised model content from two parts Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) and Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (Bi-LSTM) neural networks. EMD approach enhance the prediction accuracy especially short-term prediction because is applied as un-supervised learning to extract the features, frequency and amplitude the second part Bi-LSTM work as supervised learning to predict PM_{2.5} concentration in Beijing in 2020. The indicator values that were used for hourly prediction were (RMSE: 6.86 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, MAE: 4.92 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, MAPE: 10.66%, R²: 0.989) and daily (RMSE: 22.58 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, MAE: 16.67 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, MAPE: 60.87%, R²: 0.742). This model maybe reduces error accumulation in PM_{2.5}.

An improved deep learning model for predicting daily PM_{2.5} concentration[23]. In this paper to forecast the daily constriction of PM_{2.5} in Beijing–Tianjin–Hebei they proposed new model called Weighted Long Short-Term Memory Neural Network Extended model (WLSTME). Monitoring stations are unequally distributed so first to combine wind speed and wind direction with the PM_{2.5} data a multilayer perception (MLP) was used. As a second step entering weighted data of PM_{2.5} into LSTM processing it with spatial and temporal dependence, and extracting temporal and spatial features. The final step is to combine meteorological data with spatiotemporal features with the central sites. The evaluation metrics that used to this model and got this result RMSE (40.67), MAE (26.10) and p (0.59). WLSTME improve the accuracy especially in winter.

Air Pollution Prediction by Deep Learning Model [25]. In this paper predicted PM_{2.5} by using bidirectional long short-term memory (Bi-LSTM) model. The proposed model achieved accuracy as follows MAE (7.53), RMSE (9.86) and SMAPE (0.1664).

Real Time Attention Based Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory Networks for Air Pollution Forecasting[26]. 2019, Delhi, proposed Bi-LSTM model to forecasting real time air quality to three pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂) and also a classification of the level of risk caused after the next 24 hours.

Deep Air: Air Quality Prediction using Deep Neural Network [34], and Air Quality Index forecasting using parallel Dense Neural Network and LSTM cell[35]. to predict PM_{2.5} Concentrations in New Delhi [34] and Beijing [35] they purposed Long Short-Term Memory model with Deep Neural Network (LSTN-DNN) and using RMSE as evaluation metrics.

3.2 Spatiotemporal deep learning

Spatiotemporal(ST) data are spatial locations that correspond to multiple time series. This type of data is found in many dynamic systems such as air quality readings [27]. Spatiotemporal Deep Learning (STDL) mainly includes a spatial module, a deduction module and a temporal prediction module to deal with spatiotemporal features. One of the advantages of DTDL networks is to better extract the spatiotemporal features from the data, which is why it is supposed to achieve better prediction performance than temporal structures such as LSTM [28].

Spatiotemporal prediction of air quality based on LSTM neural network [19]. In this paper the researchers proposed a new model based on LSTM which is Multi-output and Multi-index of Supervised Learning (MMSL) to predicted air quality for next 9h the mode work by collecting the data from different station in Beijing that included meteorological data and gaseous pollutant data into the model to realize the concentration prediction of air quality indicators and also the pollution indicator of PM_{2.5}, CO, NO₂, O₃, SO₂.MAE, RMSE and R2 were used as evaluation metrics. The result showed the efficiency of MMSL model.

Regional air quality forecasting using spatiotemporal deep learning[22]. Delhi 2020 to forecast Air Quality Index (AQI), Abirami and Chitra proposed hybrid deep learning model (DL-Air) model. The proposed model consists of three components (encoder, STAA-LSTM and decoder). Encoding by encoding all related spatial relationships into the underlying space input. And yet the STAA-LSTM defines the relevant temporal relationships of the latent space. furthermore, they predict future spatiotemporal relations which are expediently decoded by the decoder to gain the predicted air quality values. DL-Air use different evaluation metrics which is (RMSE, MAE, AAD and R2). DL-Air Reduce error by 30% and improved accuracy by 8%.

Modeling Air Quality Prediction using a Deep Learning approach: Method Optimization and Evaluation [24]. In

this research, they predicted $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations at 24 hours in Jing-Jin-Ji region, using temporal sliding long short-term memory extended model (TS-LSTME) model. Most of the research failed to achieve the spatiotemporal correlations of air quality monitoring stations. This model attempts to solve this problem. TS-LSTME integrates the prediction interval through a multi-layer bidirectional LSTM that includes temporal data, PM concentrations per hour and also meteorological data. R^2 was used as evaluation metrics and it achieved good results compared to MLR.

Deep Air Learning: Interpolation, Prediction, and Feature Analysis of Fine-Grained Air Quality[33]. Deep Air Learning (DAL) model was proposed in this paper to analysis fine-grained air quality in Beijing, China by using spatiotemporal data (ST) and hourly polluted data ($PM_{2.5}$, SO_2 , NO_2 , CO, PM_{10} , O_3). DAL works by selecting and embedding features in semi-supervised learning and is placed in different layers of a deep learning network.

3.3 Convolutional neuron network (CNN)

They are deep feed networks consisting of a series of convolutional layers used to extract the spatial features of neural networks. Samples are taken between two consecutive convolutional layers. These samples are used for maximal and intermediate aggregation. CNN achieved remarkable results in multi-dimensional spatial arrays used in speech and image recognition [45][52]. This makes it a good topic for researchers to know the environmental situation through digital images. CNN have the ability to effectively extract the spatial characteristics of pollutants [42].

Spatiotemporal Deep Learning Model for Citywide Air Pollution Interpolation and Prediction[29]. Seoul city in Korea, they considered a city as a single image using CNN to solve the problem of Air Pollution Interpolation and prediction. Then they used the spatiotemporal data(ST), which includes air pollution data, meteorological data, traffic volume, average driving speed and air pollution indicators in outdoor areas. These spatiotemporal data were used in the proposed model which is the Convolutional Long Short-Term Memory (Conv-LSTM) which has proven its superiority over the various models.

Deep Air Quality Forecasts: Suspended Particulate Matter Modeling with Convolutional Neural and Long Short-Term Memory Networks [37]. to forecast Total Suspended Particulate (TSP) for next hour. TSP is a measure of the masses of PM particles in the air. They developed a hybrid CLSTM model where it merges CNN with long short-term memory (LSTM) network. The hybrid model been compared with different machine learning technic and by using six evaluation metrics (R, RMSE, MAE, WI, L, E_{NS}).

Adaptive Deep Learning-Based Air Quality Prediction Model Using the Most Relevant Spatial-Temporal Relations [38]. In this study proposed a new adaptive deep learning model named spatial-temporal deep neural network (ST-DNN) to forecast $PM_{2.5}$ Concentrations for the next 48 hours. ST-DNN Housed many of neural networks its ANN, CNN, LSTM to extract spatial-temporal relations. The model was training on data from two different city whose is Taiwan and Beijing

3.4 Stacked Autoencoder (SAE)

An autoencoder is an NN that attempts to reproduce its input [46]. It has the ability to extract advantages in small spaces by reconstructing the inputs. SAE is a stacking of successive layers of autoencoders devices[18]. For a SAE with M hidden layer, the autoencoders perform unsupervised pre-training from hidden layer k ($k < M$) to hidden layer ($k + 1$). Each hidden layer is a higher-level abstraction of the previous layer, and the final hidden layer contains high-level feature which is more effective for prediction [42].

Air Pollution Prediction Using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Deep Autoencoder (DAE) Models[18]. To prediction $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} constriction for 10 days in Seoul, South Korea they use long short-term memory (LSTM) and Deep Autoencoder (DAE) methods. DAE is a type of neural network architecture, The hidden layers are stacked hierarchically within the DAE, so the final hidden layer is a higher-level representation of all layers of input, and may be used in forecasting by the DAE model begins by pre-training a single input layer, followed by hidden layers, such that the output of the kth hidden layer is used as input for the ($k + 1$)th hidden layer. The result was compared between LSTM and DAE by using RMAE they found that LSTM give result more accurate.

Deep learning architecture for air quality predictions [30]. Herein proposed deep learning architecture content STSL data and Stacked Autoencoder (SAE). Autoencoder is type of unsupervised learning included two-part encoder and decoder [31]. So, the SAE is actually a concatenation of autoencoders which the outputs of the autoencoder stacked on the layer below are wired to the inputs of the successive layer [32]. This model found to predict $PM_{2.5}$ Concentrations in China.

3.5 Others Studies

A Deep Learning-Based Prediction and Simulator of Harmful Air Pollutants: A Case from the Philippines[36]. In this study in Philippines tries to predicted SO₂ and NO₂ AQI by using DNN and simulator the result for the next 12 months.

Deep Multi-Task Learning Based Urban Air Quality Index Modelling[39]. Hangzhou city, china to solve problem of fine-grained AQI level estimation task and AQI forecasting task they propose deep multi-task learning (MTL) based on Air Quality Index (AQI) by the modeling method called PANDA.

A PM_{2.5} concentration prediction model based on multi-task deep learning for intensive air quality monitoring stations[40]. Based on Multi-Task-Deep learning (MTD) they proposed a hybrid model content shared layer whose Convolution neuron network (CNN), task-specific layer which is Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) and multi-loss joint optimization module.

Hybrid model of Air Quality Prediction Using K-Means Clustering and Deep Neural Network[41]. To predicted air quality for different pollution (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, CO, SO₂, O₃, and NO₂) they proposed hybrid model included K-Means clustering and Bi-LSTM. K-Means is back to unsupervised learning method they used this algorithm to classify meteorological data According to its features.

Hybrid Spatio-temporal Deep Learning Framework for Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5}) Concentration Forecasting [42]. by using IOT sensor data from 9 location in India to forecasting PM_{2.5} Concentration they proposed a hybrid model is CNN-LSTM.

4 Discussion

Many papers that predict air quality using deep learning techniques according to Table (1) in which we compared between (year, case study, method and model, evaluation metrics, prediction target, time step, data rates. We noted that 1- China covers most studies on air pollution [11, 14], followed by India in terms of number 2- Most of the studies focused on predicting the air quality index of PM_{2.5} [12, 14] 3- Most of all data are readings in hours 4- Prediction rates range from one hour to the next 24 hours, and some studies have predicted the air quality index for 48 hours. 5- The techniques and algorithms used to predict air quality differ as LSTM, STDL, DAL and CNN.

Table 1. Features of the selected papers

No.	Years	Case Study	Methods and Models	Evaluation Metrics	Prediction Target	Time Granularity	Data Rates	work
1.	2018	Aarhus and Brasov in Denmark and Romania	LSTM	RMSE, MAE	O ₃ , NO ₂		Hourly	[10]
2.	2017	Hong Kong, China	LSTM, M-BP		PM _{2.5} , NO ₂ , SO ₂ , PM ₁₀	5h	Hourly	[11]
3.	2018	South Korea	RNN, LSTM (En-De) model	RMSE, MAE	PM _{2.5} AQI	6h,12h,16h, 20h,24h	Hourly	[12]
4.	2018	Kuwait	RNN, LSTM	MAE	O ₃	8h	Hourly	[13]
5.	2019	Guangdong, China	TL-BLSTM	RMSE, MAE, MAPE	PM _{2.5}		Hourly	[14]
6.	2020	Taiwan	ALSTM	MAE, RMSE, MAPE	PM _{2.5}	1-8 h		[16]
7.	2020	Seoul, South Korea	DAE&LSTM	RMSE	PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀	10 days	Hourly	[17]
8.	2020	China	MMSL model based on LSTM	MAE, RMSE, R ²	PM _{2.5} , NO ₂ , CO, O ₃ , SO ₂		Hourly	[18]

9.	2020	Beijing	EMD, Bi-LSTM	RMSE, MAPE, R ² , MAE	PM _{2.5}	Hourly, Daily	Hourly, Daily	[19]
10.	2020	Beijing	Bi-LSTM Auto-Encoder	RMSE	PM _{2.5}		Hourly	[20]
11.	2020	Beijing, Tianjin – Hebei	WLSTME model	RMSE, MAE, P	PM _{2.5}		Daily	[22]
12.	2020	Jing – Jinn – Ji, China	Temporal Sliding TS-LSTME	MAE, R ² , NRMSE	PM _{2.5}	24h	Hourly	[23]
13.	2020		Bi-LSTM	RMSE, MAE, SMAPE	PM _{2.5}			[24]
14.	2019	Delhi	Bi-LSTM	RMSE, R ²	PM ₁₀ , PM _{2.5} , NO ₂	Real time, 24h	Hourly	[25]
15.	2020	Seoul city in Korea	STDN, Conv LSTM	RMSE	PM _{2.5}		Hourly	[29]
16.	2016	Beijing	STDN+SAE	RMSE, MAE, MAPE	PM _{2.5}		Hourly	[30]
17.	2018	Beijing	DAL	RMSE	PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , NO ₂ , CO ₂ , O ₃ , SO ₂	1h-48h	Hourly	[33]
18.	2019	New Delhi, India	LSTM, DNN	RMSE	PM _{2.5}	23h	Real time	[34]
19.	2020	Beijing	LSTM, DNN	MAE	PM _{2.5}	1h, 24h	Hourly	[35]
20.	2020	Philippines	DNN		SO ₂ , NO ₂	12 month		[36]
21.	2020	Queensland, Australia	CLSTM (CNN, LSTM)	R, RMSE, MAE, WI, L, E _{NS}	TSP, PM _{2.5}	1h	Hourly	[37]
22.	2018	Taiwan, Beijing	ST-DNN (ANN, CNN, LSTM)	RMSE, MAE	PM _{2.5}	48h	Hourly	[38]
23.	2019	Hangzhou, china	Deep MTL, PANDA	MAE, simi-EP	AQI	1h, 12h, 24h, 48h	Hourly	[39]
24.	2020	Lanzhou, china	MTD, CNN, GRU	RMSE, MAE	PM _{2.5}		Hourly	[40]
25.	2019	Qingdao, China	K-Means, Bi-LSTM	MAE	PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , NO ₂ , CO ₂ , O ₃ , SO ₂	24h	Hourly	[41]
26.	2020	India	CNN-LSTM	RMSE, MAE, R	PM _{2.5}	24h	Hourly	[42]

are used. We find that the models developed using LSTM give the best results and through [10,12], and also find that the RSME values represent the success of these models that achieve better results for short-term prediction. Although the diversity in deep learning techniques for predicting air quality, we find many gaps and not taking full advantage of the power of deep learning to perfectly to predict air quality in an excellent way. Since there is no clear network to extract the spatiotemporal features found in large, high-dimensional data sets, it is necessary at the outset to create comprehensive standard datasets for the design of the deep network structure and to test deep learning algorithms that include pollutants from all sources, meteorological fields, and emission source. However, there are some studies that use varied and comprehensive data such as the use of STDN and CNN-LSTM [42,29,38]. By using deep gutter techniques, the level of prediction should be improved in addition to expanding the range of medium and long-term forecasts over a period of 7 to 20 days, as well as

forecasting pollution in local areas and their complex terrain. We hope that through the combination of heterogeneous information and smart modeling of processes.

5 Conclusions

After reviewing specific papers that apply deep learning techniques to predict air pollution in smart cities, deep learning has the ability to extract complex information from big data, it can be said that deep learning is a general-purpose method and can be used in various fields of research. The use of forecasting air pollution is still in its beginnings and needs further development by building deep networks that better represent the spatiotemporal features of pollutant evolution across multiple scales. Deep learning can improve air quality prediction in various aspects such as the algorithms that are used for forecasting, source estimates, and filling data gaps. Despite all this, we find there is a large gap in the data used for comprehensive studies, as there is not yet any common data set to test deep learning algorithms through which to measure Performance for better predictions. On the other hand, we note that studies dealing with meteorology and pollutant monitoring from networks at the ground level are limited, so comprehensive data sets and deep networks must be compared and deep learning algorithms devised to obtain the best features through the metrics hidden in these comprehensive data. Finally, to overcome the problem of air pollution, which can be considered a vital thing to control future levels of air pollution in the long term, such as from 7-20 days, open problems should be proposed to stimulate the study of deep learning to predict air pollution, and break traditional methods of forecasting.

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